

ONE HEALTH-BASED STRATEGIES IN PREVENTION AND CONTROL OF RABIES IN INDIA: OVERVIEW AND FUTURE PROSPECTS

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ABSTRACT

Animals are the source of 60% of known infectious diseases in humans and more than 75% of newly emerging infectious diseases. Among these zoonoses, rabies is of paramount public health concern because to its lethality. A multi-sectoral One Health Approach may be a better way to deal with rabies because of the complex nature of zoonotic illness, which makes management and prevention more difficult. Currently, mass vaccination of domestic and community dogs and cats as well as mass awareness campaigns are used in rabies prevention and control initiatives. However, these methods have not included all stakeholders (human, animal, and environmental health sectors) in disease control programs, which has resulted in a continued burden of rabies. This review's objective is to demonstrate why and how the One Health Approach offers the best chance of controlling rabies in India and other developing nations.

KEYWORDS: India, One Health, Public health, Rabies

INTRODUCTION

Rabies is an acute, lethal zoonotic infectious disease caused by rabies virus (RABV) infection, and is one of the oldest and most terrifying diseases known to humans (Zhang et al., 2018). The Lyssavirus rabies, a single negative-stranded RNA virus in the Rhabdoviridae family, invades the central nervous system through bites or scratches from infected animals or through contamination of fresh wounds or mucous membranes by infectious material (Hemachudha et al., 2013). Once a human is bitten by a rabid animal, the clinical manifestations are mainly manical. When clinical signs such as hydrophobia, photophobia, and laryngeal spasm emerge, the disease becomes usually fatal despite advanced medical interventions (Abdulmajid & Hassan, 2021). The Lyssavirus rabies can infect all mammals; however, the domestic dog is the principal reservoir host of the virus (Briggs et al., 2018).

Over 7 million people worldwide are exposed to the Lyssavirus rabies due to dog bites

every year, resulting in 59,000 deaths, and this number is considered to be an underestimate (Smreczak & Żmudziński 2019; Ehrenberg et al., 2021). Unfortunately, most cases of rabies occur in the poorest and most vulnerable communities in the world (Chen et al., 2017). Approximately 40% of the victims are children under the age of 15 living in Asia and Africa (Cleaveland et al., 2002). However, the 100% fatality of this disease is counterbalanced by its 100% preventability, which encompasses both individual and collective understanding. Research has shown that receiving rabies vaccination (with additional equine anti-rabies serum for severely bitten patients) following an animal bite can generate effective antibodies and prevent the occurrence of fatalities, regardless of the severity of the case (Warrell et al., 1985).

A more realistic approach to prevention may be the goal of eliminating rabies, but this depends on the implementation of various necessary measures, including policies, economic

considerations, and execution. For example, by implementing dog vaccination and population management programs, almost every high-income country has eliminated dog-mediated rabies (Velasco-Villa et al., 2017). Recent research on rabies has produced strong evidence to demonstrate the feasibility of eliminating canine rabies through large-scale vaccination of domestic dogs (Cleaveland and Hampson, 2017). The International Task Force on the Elimination of Diseases (ITFDE) defines seven curable diseases and advises bodies such as the World Health Organization on various aspects of disease eradication. Eliminating any infectious disease worldwide is a difficult undertaking, made considerably more difficult by the interaction of social variables and the inherent traits of certain viruses. A global goal to eradicate dog-mediated human rabies deaths by 2030 has been set by the World Health Organization (WHO), the World Organization for Animal Health (OIE), the Food and Agricultural Organization of the United Nations (FAO), and the Global Alliance for Rabies Control (GARC) (Wallace et al., 2017).

Building on these efforts, incorporating the One Health Approach into rabies management plans can provide a mechanism to not only deal with the present issue but also foresee potential future rabies concerns. Due to its interdisciplinary approach to treating and managing zoonotic and vector-borne diseases worldwide, the One Health Approach has been increasingly popular in recent years. Enhancing human, animal, and environmental health, improving disease understanding and prediction, controlling diseases across species, and maximizing resource usage through multi-sector collaboration are the main objectives of this method. By putting the concept into practice, Asian nations may enhance surveillance, immunization campaigns, and public education regarding rabies prevention, which is essential for tackling the more than 95% of cases that result from dog bites using a multipronged approach. The One Health concept surfaces as a promising framework in recognition of the many issues rabies poses in India, ranging from the disease's high prevalence and financial burden to the requirement for better public health measures. This scoping review's main goal is to assess and summarize how well One Health strategies work to manage rabies in different parts of India.

TRANSMISSION OF RABIES

Numerous mammals, such as dogs, foxes, wolves, jackals, raccoons, skunks, mongoose, and many bat species, can act as reservoir hosts for the rabies virus, which subsequently spreads to other mammals (Müller & Freuling et al., 2025). Humans can contract RABV through three main routes: bites, exposure to mucosal membranes, and, less frequently, inhalation of aerosols. The most frequent method of infection and transmission occurs when a rabid animal bites a person, causing saliva containing the rabies virus to enter the victim's muscular and subcutaneous tissues through the skin. Because dogs are closely associated with humans, the majority of diseases are spread through dog bites. An undamaged skin is typically immune to the virus. Scratches are necessary, even though scratches contaminated with infectious saliva are a less common mode of transmission because the infection risk is several times lower than that of genuine bites. After a minor bite that goes unnoticed, skin exposure may result in subcutaneous infection. The way that bat-transmitted RABV enters the central nervous system from cutaneous nerves is still unclear, albeit (Mahadevan et al., 2016). People who live close to caves where many infected bats reside and laboratory workers who unintentionally come into contact with RABV when homogenizing goat brains for the production of rabies vaccine have been related to aerosolized RABV spread by inhalation (Agarwal et al., 2023). Rarely can human-to-human transmission occur, and all known cases are iatrogenic after organs taken from unidentified, rabies-infected donors were transplanted.

GLOBAL SITUATION OF RABIES

In almost every land mass, rabies is endemic, with the exception of islands like Australia and Antarctica, where no cases of dog-mediated rabies have been documented (Singh et al., 2017; Hampson et al., 2015). Although many Asian, European, North American, and South American nations have been deemed rabies-free (Singh et al., 2017; Yousaf et al., 2012) rabies remains a concern in many Asian and African nations. The prevalence of rabies is moderate in Nepal, Myanmar, Bhutan, Thailand, and Indonesia, and extremely high in Bangladesh and India (Singh et al., 2017; Hampson et al., 2015). According to reports, between 0 and 55% of canine rabies cases worldwide occur in Asian subcontinental countries (Hampson et al., 2015).

RABIES IN INDIA

Human cases of rabies are reported all year round in India, which is endemic with the exception of the Andaman & Nicobar and Lakshadweep Islands. India is responsible for 65% of human rabies deaths in South East Asia and 36% of rabies deaths worldwide, according to WHO estimates 2018. About 96% of rabies-related deaths and morbidities in India are caused by dog bites, with children being the most susceptible demographic, accounting for 40% of dog bite victims in rabies-endemic areas (WHO, 2018). Different studies give different numbers for the number of human rabies deaths and animal bites. While the 50 million deaths study in 2012 indicated 12,700 deaths from ferocious rabies, the WHO-APCRI 2004 study estimated 17.4 million animal (Sudarshan et al., 2007) bites and 20,000 deaths annually in India (Suraweera et al., 2012).

Incidence of Human Rabies

Various reports and studies provide estimates of human rabies deaths in India. (Figure 1) Sudarshan et al., 2007; Suraweera et al., 2012 Knobel et al., 2005; Nale et al., 20025). The Central Bureau of Health Intelligence has been monitoring human rabies cases, and the trend of reported deaths is illustrated in Figure 2 (Nale et al., 20025).

Mortality due to Human Rabies

The National Rabies Control Programme keeps tabs on the number of rabies-related fatalities in India. The reported suspected human rabies cases from 2018 to 2022 are displayed in Figure 3. A nationwide population-based assessment of the burden of human rabies and animal bites was conducted in 2023 by the National Institute of Epidemiology (NIE), Indian Council of Medical Research, Chennai, which estimated annual human rabies deaths using a decision tree probability model with parameters from the community survey and laboratory data on rabies positivity among suspected rabid dogs. The number of reported animal bites under the Integrated Disease Surveillance Programme (IDSP) has increased from 4.2 million in 2012 to 7.2 million in 2019 (Fig 4).

More than one-third of all rabies deaths worldwide occur in India. India has developed a national program to eradicate rabies (NRCP) by 2030 in order to solve this issue (MoHFW, 2021). It is essential to comprehend rabies' secular patterns during the eradication stage.

Fig. 1: Trend of Estimated Human Rabies cases in India

Fig. 2: Human Rabies Deaths reported in India (Source: CBHI)

Fig. 3: Human Rabies Cases Reported under

Fig. 4: Reported Animal Bite Incidents in India NRCP (Source: IDSP)

Trends of rabies in India

Consequently, we used information from the National Health Profile (NHP), a compilation of monthly health status reports by state from 2005 to 2020, to characterize rabies trends. By utilizing Joinpoint regression, we were able to compute incidence and determine the average annual percentage change (AAPC). From 2.36 to 0.41 cases per 10 million people, the incidence of rabies significantly decreased (AAPC = -11.3%, 95% CI: -13.9% to -8.7%, $p < 0.001$) (Fig. 4 A and B). According to the NHP, there were 2863 rabies cases in India between 2005 and 2020; more than three-fourths of the cases were in five states: West Bengal (43%), Andhra Pradesh (10%), Maharashtra (8%), Karnataka (7%), and Delhi (6%). (Fig. 4 C) (CBHI 2023). In order to ensure accurate rabies incidence data—which is essential for creating and putting into practice efficient prevention and control measures—India proclaimed human rabies to be notifiable in 2021. Between 2012 and 2022, 6644 human rabies cases were reported by the NRCP (MoHFW, 2021; Goel et al., 2023), whereas between 2005 and 2020, the NHP reported 2863 instances (CBHI, 2023). The NHP recorded 259 cases of rabies in 2005, but the One-million Death Study predicted 12,700 deaths. Traditional healers' preference for treatment and deaths that occur outside of hospitals may be the cause of the egregious underreporting (Suraweera et al., 2012). To get around these data restrictions, India has introduced the Integrated Health Information Platform (IHIP), which uses mobile applications to gather data in real time. At the moment, NRCP employs tactics including inter-sectoral coordination, improved public awareness, prophylactic vaccination for both humans and dogs, and efficient dog population control (MoHFW, 2021). Although the incidence has decreased as a result of these actions, there are still obstacles such as operational difficulties, financial limits, and public non-compliance. It's also critical to recognize and manage the function of other carriers, like monkeys and bats. These species may also serve as reservoirs for the rabies virus in some areas, which calls for more comprehensive wildlife management and surveillance plans (MoHFW, 2021). The WHO, World Organization for Animal Health, and Food and Agriculture Organization have been collaborating as part of the Tripartite alliance to manage health risks through the "One Health" approach (Goel et al., 2023). This multi-sectoral collaboration intends to cooperatively build evaluation frameworks for epidemiology and

surveillance, support a shared vision of global health security, and informed decision-making. Adopting these One Health capacity-strengthening exercises could considerably increase India's rabies control efforts and could pave the road towards the elimination of human rabies by 2030.

Fig. 4: Trends of rabies in India

ONGOING RABIES CONTROL PROGRAMS AND INITIATIVES IN INDIA

The execution of rabies control initiatives in India has been greatly aided by the National Centre for Disease Control (NCDC) in Delhi. In order to (MoHFW, 2019) standardize post-exposure prophylactic procedures, NCDC conducted a consultation in 2002 to create nationwide guidelines for rabies prophylaxis. Following the 2004 cessation of manufacture of Nervous Tissue Vaccines, these guidelines were updated in 2007 and 2013 to encourage the use of contemporary cell culture vaccines (CCVs) for post-exposure prophylaxis. However, the high expense of administering CCVs intramuscularly prevented its widespread adoption. Following WHO guidelines and a feasibility study carried out by the National Institute of Epidemiology, Chennai, in 2005, the Drugs Controller General of India (DCGI) authorized the safe, efficient, and economical intra-dermal (ID) route of CCV injection in February 2006. In 2019, the national rabies prophylactic guidelines underwent additional revisions and updates. (MoHFW, 2019) The Ministry of Health and Family Welfare allocated funds for pilot programs to control human rabies as part of the 11th Five-Year Plan (2007–2012). The Animal Welfare Board of India (AWBI) was tasked with overseeing the plan's first animal welfare elements, which included rabies prevention for animals, animal birth control, and stray dog vaccination.

From 2008 to 2012, NCDC carried out the "National Rabies Control Programme: Initiative," a trial initiative, in five cities. Among its goals were preventing rabies-related deaths in humans, increasing public awareness, educating medical professionals, fortifying diagnostic facilities, and enhancing surveillance. The National Rabies Control Programme (NRCP) was approved for nationwide implementation during the 12th Five-Year Plan after the successful pilot study confirmed the strategy's viability and reproducibility. The central government provided all of the funding for the NRCP, with the Ministry of Health & Family Welfare distributing the funds to the states and other partners. (Haradanhalli et al., 2019) In all states and union territories, the human health component of the NRCP program is being implemented by the Ministry of Health and Family Welfare. After being approved by the 8th Empowered Programme (Haradanhalli et al., 2019) Committee (EPC) meeting, state-level initiatives are executed under the National Health Mission. According to the National Health Missions Programme Implementation Plan process, funds are distributed for a range of NRCP-related initiatives at various administrative levels. The program's goal is to prevent and reduce human rabies deaths, with the ultimate goal of reaching the global target of "Rabies-Zero by 2030," beginning in fiscal year 2021, 2022.

ONE HEALTH INTERVENTIONS IN RABIES CONTROL

One Health initiatives acknowledge the interdependence of human health with that of animals and our common environment. The goal of adopting a One Health approach is to manage rabies outbreaks in both humans and animals. In addition to lowering the requirement for a post-exposure vaccine, preventing animal-to-human rabies transmission also lessens the financial burden associated with human rabies control. It is well recognized that the One Health approach is a cost-effective way to control rabies in impoverished nations like India. Before implementing the program on a bigger scale, a pilot study involving both rural and urban populations in various locations could be useful to gauge the success metrics of this strategy.

Thus, to carry out a successful strategy, an integrated approach and collaboration between the human, animal, and environmental sectors are

equally necessary. The management of the dog population and mass vaccination of animals are crucial, although the latter should adhere to animal welfare regulations. Through government measures, inhumane killing and torturing of animals must be absolutely forbidden (Acharya et al., 2019). If putting an animal down is the only alternative, then lawful euthanasia should be used in its place (Neupane, 2019). Legislation requiring required registration can also make records of pet ownership and public safety accessible. Animal birth control methods like spaying and castration can also be used to limit the number of street or community dogs (Acharya et al., 2019). Prior to these activities, an effective data collection and reporting system is required.

Public participation is the program's primary determinant of success. A number of awareness efforts can be used to increase participation. Program execution will also be determined by the accessibility of essential infrastructure, including roads, electricity, hospitals, and veterinary clinics. Participation in mass vaccination, post-exposure vaccination, and animal birth control programs may be influenced by an individual's economic standing and level of literacy (Lechenne et al., 2017). Human, animal, environmental, and socioeconomic aspects are important, though not always the only ones to take into account. Thus, a "Multi-sectoral One Health Approach" might be a powerful tactic to achieve measurable advancements in rabies prevention and control. In a number of nearby nations, including Bangladesh, Sri Lanka, and Bhutan, a One Health concept has shown promise. Bhutan has only reported 17 cases of rabies between 2006 and 2016 (Acharya et al., 2020; Tenzin et al., 2017). Similarly, a One Health multi-sectoral approach was first tested in small rural communities before being successfully expanded to the entire country of Bangladesh, which reduced rabies deaths from 1500 in 2012 to 200 in 2015. Sri Lanka also reported that they were able to reduce rabies deaths to less than 50 in 2012 by implementing a mass vaccination program in dogs. Most significantly, India recently finished a trial of this management approach in five different cities throughout the country and concluded that taking into account both human and animal components is crucial. The "One Health Approach," which entails cross-sectoral cooperation between animal, human, and environmental health, can effectively prevent or manage rabies. Given the

unique geopolitical circumstances of the country, the following actions may be useful to ensure the program's success in India.

Systematic data collection and compilation

A regular reporting system that allows for the assessment of disease's socioeconomic burden, endemic and sporadic status, and periodic progress is ideal for a One Health strategy. The development of national control plans or strategies will benefit greatly from this information (Fahrion et al., 2017). Since rabies symptoms are non-specific or similar to those of other nervous system illnesses, it is not surprising that rabies cases may go unreported. This problem worsens when hospitals and tertiary care clinics' registration facilities are unable to access databases for clinical care and diagnostic confirmation (Fahrion et al., 2017). Therefore, a system that offers precise data on the number of dogs, rabies cases that are suspected or confirmed, and the total number of people infected with rabies at a specific location and time would be useful in creating control plans (Fahrion et al., 2017). The efficiency of rabies control programs also depends on the calculation of human-dog population densities, statistics on animal and human vaccination, and thorough data management and analysis.

Co-ordination and data sharing among animal, human and environmental health sectors

Projects needing multi-sectoral coordination frequently suffer from a lack of coordination and data sharing amongst interested parties. It will be easier to identify problem areas and develop management strategies if primary data is gathered, stored, and reported in national and international databases. Rabies is not a common disease in many nations. As a result, only official monitoring systems in these nations are able to collect data on rabies. Operational challenges in submitting samples to the laboratory and non-compliance with direct data reporting to line ministries may make rabies monitoring in India further challenging. This will make it more likely that inaccurate and partial data will be generated.

Efficient and effective surveillance

The primary focus of India's animal health sector is livestock diseases that have a significant economic impact. That list does not include rabies (WHO, 2012). Adding rabies to the list of illnesses the Animal Health Sector monitors would facilitate the gathering of trustworthy data for population control and mass vaccine

planning. According to Banyard and his colleagues (Banyard et al., 2013) a robust surveillance system that produces primary data is essential to achieving protective immunological state of sensitive animal populations and transmission.

Fig. 5: Conceptual framework on how to control rabies using One Health Approach.

Given the close proximity of humans, domestic animals, and wildlife territories, controlling rabies in wildlife and the wildlife-domestic animal interface may be essential to rabies control in India. In order to effectively prevent rabies from spreading from wildlife to domestic animals and people, rabies monitoring and control efforts must be expanded to include wildlife. Large-scale oral vaccination campaigns with at least 70% coverage, taking into account the ecological and epidemiological characteristics of rabies and wildlife species (Eisinger & Thulke 2008) could be one strategy to control wildlife rabies. This approach has been successfully used in coyotes in the United States (Elmore et al., 2017), raccoons in Canada and foxes in Europe (Eisinger & Thulke 2008). Bait containing the oral rabies vaccination (ORV) can be placed in natural habitat, including a buffer zone, national parks and wildlife reserves, community woods, and suburban areas. Reducing the potential for rabies to spread from livestock to humans and vice versa may be beneficial.

Sufficiency and availability of post exposure prophylaxis (PEP)

After a dog bite, PEP is the only way to prevent rabies in humans. Naturally, the burden of rabies will be greater if PEP is unavailable right after a suspected rabid animal bites. Both government and private hospitals in metropolitan areas offer PEP and pre-exposure prophylaxis (PrEP) (Lechenne et al., 2017). However, many reasons in remote locations do not have easy access to PrEP and PEP. Rural residents find it challenging to get treatment when bitten because

medical facilities are now primarily located in urban areas (Lechenne et al., 2017). Making sure PEP is sufficiently available is essential to achieving zero rabies-related deaths in humans by 2030. Another strategy to save more lives in the near future is the integrated dog bite case management (IBCM) approach, which links rabies surveillance personnel in the veterinary and public health sectors to evaluate the risk of rabies among animal bite victims and biting animals (Undurraga et al., 2017). Together, effective local, national, and international actions can achieve long-term, sustainable rabies control.

Increasing vaccine coverage

One economical method of rabies control is mass dog vaccination. As per the World Health Organization (WHO) and the Organization for Animal Health (OIE), a vaccination rate of at least 70% in dogs can quickly reduce the rate of infection. Human exposure will be directly reduced as a result. Long-term benefits of investing in dog vaccination, particularly mass vaccination, include increased cost-efficiency (Zinsstag et al., 2009). Therefore, one of the main strategies we recommend to prevent rabies in both human and animal populations is mass dog vaccination. This strategy will be more successful if domesticated and stray dogs are properly registered, confined, and vaccinated. It's also important to have follow-up booster shots because dogs that don't get them will not be fully inoculated. Infections with rabies can still occur in this situation even after vaccination.

Increasing efficacy of vaccination

One of the most crucial rabies prevention strategies is vaccination. Immunity may not be evoked by vaccinations given below the recommended level. In addition to manufacturing flaws, improper handling, storage, and transportation are the most frequent causes of vaccination failure. Therefore, in order for rabies control efforts to be successful, both vaccine efficacy and quality are equally important.

Increasing awareness

Programs to raise public awareness that target vulnerable areas will be crucial in the fight against any disease epidemic, including rabies. Nepali communities are somewhat ignorant about rabies. Numerous factors, such as the low literacy rate, socioeconomic problems, and rabies's lack of priority disease classification, could be to blame for this. To improve the situation, however, information about dog vaccination, PEP

availability, and dog bite prevention strategies may be useful (Balaram et al., 2016).

Strengthening laboratory capacity

Having well-equipped laboratories can improve diagnostic capabilities. It is crucial to implement preventative and control measures (such as a vaccination program or a full package project) for rabies before exposure (Aga et al., 2016). In this sense, targeted vaccination coverage and assessment could be accomplished with the use of locally accessible diagnostic services (Lembo, et al., 2010). Major Indian cities have a few well-equipped labs that satisfy OIE standards, but there is potential for improvement to make them more accessible. The burden for these labs may be somewhat reduced by adopting fast test kits for initial screening, but there are no other options due to the lack of necessary laboratory facilities. It is assumed that the accuracy of disease diagnosis will be low when it is based solely on clinical signs and symptoms. This being stated, improved identification and reporting depend on both the price of the service and the availability of a trustworthy diagnosis (Hossain et al., 2012).

Research activities

Finding related risk factors, the predominant mechanism of transmission, socioeconomic ramifications, and disease dynamics based on locality may be aided by epidemiology field study on rabies. Therefore, carrying out this study could be a great place to start when developing integrated multi-sectoral rabies management plans. The following are some important areas of research interventions and innovations:

- (1) creation of instruments to gauge the severity of rabies infections.
- (2) The availability of affordable and simple diagnostic tests.
- (3) Research that promotes "soft" population control measures such responsible dog ownership, dog population control, and environmental elements of rabies management.
- (4) Regular gathering of information on the fundamental population characteristics of pertinent animal species, such as dog populations (size, turnover, accessibility, and ownership status) in various contexts.

Fig. 6. Conceptual framework on how to control of human rabies. (The green lines are risk reduction options and the red lines are risk factors).

(5) Public awareness campaigns to promote knowledge of PEP, first aid and animal bite management.

(6) Raising awareness on the disease and responsible dog ownership with active mobilization of NGOs, community-based organizations, animal welfare societies, media, leaders, and other influential groups.

CONCLUSION

In the great majority of nations across the world, rabies still poses a threat to people's health and lives, resulting in unimaginable financial costs. A multifaceted strategy is necessary to reduce the spread of rabies globally, and in India specifically. Run awareness programs to inform communities—especially those in rural areas—about safe animal-interaction techniques and how cultural customs can lower the danger of rabies transmission. Encourage the prudent management of the dog population: To stop the spread of rabies, put in place thorough dog population control methods that include vaccination programs, sterilization, and responsible dog ownership. Establish comprehensive environmental monitoring initiatives to detect alterations that could affect reservoir species distribution and, in turn, rabies transmission. The Alliance Against Rabies helps nations create workable and viable solutions by using a One-Health concept. There have been some successful cases recently. The One Health India action plan is a paradigm of leadership in India, and it can serve as a model for other rabies-endemic nations by 2030. India can play a significant role in accomplishing this global goal because it bears around one-third of the world's rabies burden. India has prioritized the prevention of this avoidable illness. We can considerably lower the rabies burden and get closer to a world free of this terrible illness by implementing these suggestions.

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